

Before first observed prison or jail contact: health and social strain trajectories in HILDA

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Sergey Alexeev^{a,b,1}, Caitlin Davey^c, Diksha Sapkota^c, Jesse Young^d, James Ogilvie^c, Evelyn Lee^b, Rachel Sutherland^a, Zheng Guo^e, Benjamin Spivak^f, Donald Weatherburn^a, Steve Larkin^g, Carleen Thompson^c, and Robert Breunig^h

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Background. Prison or jail contact is often observed after health and social circumstances have already begun to deteriorate, but the pre-contact period is usually treated as a methodological nuisance. Using 24 waves of the Household, Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia (HILDA) Survey, we describe those years and their implications for prevention and for causal claims from general-population panels.

Methods. Among 50,403 respondents in the HILDA responding-adult spine (2001–2024), 630 ever reported prison or jail contact in the previous 12 months. We estimated unweighted event-time means for psychological distress (Kessler 10, K10), Short-Form 36 (SF-36) health domains, self-rated health, smoking, employment, financial strain, loneliness, and body mass index, and a six-domain cumulative observed strain index (the share of observed respondent-level domains in the adverse range).

Results. The strain index rose from 41% adverse components at least six years before first observed contact to 53% in the contact window (the year of first report and the year before it). The largest pre-contact changes were in K10 (+3.5 points on the 10–50 scale), SF-36 mental health (-6.8 on the 0–100 scale), employment (-18.1 percentage points, pp), smoking (+6.6 pp), financial strain (+7.8 pp), and loneliness (+0.3 on a 1–7 scale). Physical-health domains deteriorated more gradually and persistently, without the same short-run escalation in strain; body mass index did not deteriorate.

Conclusions. First observed respondent prison or jail contact in HILDA sits near the visible peak of a multi-domain health and social strain process, not its onset. Multi-domain strain is detectable in routine panel measures years before contact, raising questions about where health and social services intersect with people before custody. National household panels with self-completion exposure and no first-lifetime indicator are structurally weak for causal estimation of incarceration effects because the exposure can miss much of the trajectory it would need to net out. Pre-contact dynamics are the signal, not a nuisance.

1. Introduction

Successive surveys of the Australian prison population have repeatedly shown that people entering or in prison are characterised by poor physical and mental health, widespread homelessness and unemployment, high levels of drug and alcohol problems, and frequent prior episodes of imprisonment [1]. In most cases, these findings are used to underscore the social and economic disadvantage of the prison population, or to motivate in-prison and post-release efforts to remediate these problems [2–4]. The evidence is usually drawn from cross-sectional surveys of people entering or already in custody. Little attention is given to changes in health and social circumstances in the period preceding first entry, even though this period might provide more fertile ground for intervention: to reduce the likelihood of imprisonment or, at the very least, to improve outcomes for those who are eventually incarcerated.

Highlights

- Observed health and social strain accumulates for years before first observed prison or jail contact, not just at it.
- The escalation is concentrated in distress, employment, smoking, finances, and loneliness; physical health changes little in the short run and BMI not at all.
- Multi-domain strain is detectable in routine survey data before custody; HILDA cannot show whether services were available or used.
- National household panels are structurally weak for causal estimation of incarceration effects on health.
- Pre-contact dynamics are a core descriptive signal, not a nuisance to be controlled away.

Author affiliations: ^aUNSW Sydney, Australia; ^bThe University of Sydney, Australia; ^cGriffith University, Australia; ^dUniversity of Toronto, Canada; ^eUniversity of Malaya, Malaysia; ^fSwinburne University of Technology, Australia; ^gAdelaide University, Australia; ^hThe Australian National University, Australia

¹To whom correspondence should be addressed: sergey.alexeev@sydney.edu.au.

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A recent Australian synthesis confirms that, despite growth in prison health research, longitudinal evidence on health trajectories before, during, and after incarceration remains limited [5].

Terminology matters for this paper. We use *prison or jail contact* because that is the wording of the HILDA life-event item. The item asks whether the respondent had been in prison or jail in the previous 12 months. In the Australian context, we do not use “prison” and “jail” as a clean institutional distinction; the phrase is a survey measure of respondent self-reported custody contact in the prior year.

A central difficulty is temporal ordering. Poor health among people with prison or jail contact may reflect health-damaging effects of incarceration, but it may also reflect health and social trajectories already underway before custody is observed. The few longitudinal and life-course studies available show that much incarceration-related health disadvantage predates formal custody, especially for psychiatric disorders, substance use, and poverty [6, 7]. To understand the impact of prison on health, we first need to understand health trajectories before custody is observed. This matters for population health because the period before custody may itself be a period of escalating health and social strain, not only a source of bias to be controlled away.

Panel-data designs have been central to research on incarceration and health. Fixed-effects models, hybrid models, before-after comparisons, and event-study designs are useful because they use repeated observations to move beyond simple cross-sectional differences between people who do and do not experience incarceration [8–10]. Stronger quasi-experimental designs, such as studies using natural experiments or quasi-random variation in detention, are powerful because they seek variation less entangled with the health trajectory leading into custody [10, 11]. However, the interpretation of panel estimates depends on how the event is timed and on what is happening before the event. Fixed effects remove stable between-person differences; they do not automatically remove time-varying pre-contact change. Event-study designs can show such dynamics, but only if pre-contact trends are interpreted rather than treated as a routine assumption check.

This paper therefore asks a descriptive question that is logically prior to causal estimation: where does first observed entry into custody sit within respondents’ longer-term health and social trajectories? We use 24 annual waves (2001–2024) of the Household, Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia (HILDA) Survey, a national household panel with repeated health, labour-market, income, and social measures [12–14]. The HILDA prison or jail item is a past-year self-reported life-event measure from the self-completion questionnaire (SCQ). Throughout, *first observed contact* means the earliest HILDA wave in which a respondent reports this past-year item. It is not necessarily first lifetime incarceration. Because the item has a 12-month lookback and the exact custody date is not observed, the *contact window* in the event-time figures is the first affirmative wave and the preceding survey year, not a precisely timed custody onset.

Existing HILDA research on incarceration-related exposures has focused mainly on family-member incarceration and family outcomes. This work has shown that incarceration-related exposures are measurable in HILDA, that they are associated with health and social disadvantage, and that within-person models often attenuate cross-sectional associations [9, 15–17]. The current paper shifts the focus to respondents’ own observed prison or jail contact and describes the dynamic trajectory structure around that first observed contact.

We examine eleven outcomes spanning psychological distress, mental health, physical health, self-rated health, smoking, employment, financial strain, loneliness, and body mass index (BMI). We use *strain* as shorthand for observed health and social adversity in repeated respondent-level measures; it is operationally defined below. Using 24 waves of HILDA, we aim to describe pre-contact trajectories across these outcomes, summarise six respondent-level domains in a cumulative observed strain index, and assess what the observed trajectory structure implies for causal claims from general-population panels. We do not estimate the effect of incarceration on health.

The paper makes three contributions. First, it provides a broad descriptive account of dynamic health and social trajectories around first observed respondent prison or jail contact in HILDA. Second, it shows that the pre-contact period is substantively important for population health because several domains are already deteriorating before contact becomes visible in the panel. Third, it shows why conventional within-person panel designs are not enough in a setting where custody may follow a multi-year deterioration in health and social functioning: fixed effects and before-after contrasts remove stable differences while still missing the dynamic selection process that matters most.

2. Data and Measures

A. The HILDA Survey. We use the Household, Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia Survey, a household-based longitudinal study that began in 2001 and follows respondents annually [12, 13]. The analytic files used for this paper contain 24 waves covering 2001–2024. HILDA interviews household members aged 15 years and over and includes an annual interview and a self-completion questionnaire. The survey has broad coverage of income, employment, family life, health, health behaviours, and social circumstances, making it well suited to describing multi-domain health and social trajectories.

Our analytic spine includes all person-waves from waves A through X (waves 1–24) for individuals who were at any point classified as responding adults in the HILDA panel. Because HILDA interviews people from age 15, this file status should not be read as a clean restriction to adult prison episodes; the exposure limitation is discussed below. The spine contains 500,490 person-waves from 50,403 people. The panel is unbalanced, as expected in a long-running household survey with refreshment, attrition, intermittent non-response, and changes in household composition. The full spine is retained regardless of whether the prison or jail item is observed; it is used to define within-sample thresholds and to situate the contact group, while all trajectory analyses condition on the ever-contact group. Counts in this paper are unweighted. HILDA cross-sectional weights are designed to make each wave representative of the Australian population; the objective here is to describe the observed trajectory structure among people who ever report respondent prison or jail contact, not to estimate population prevalence, and weighting cannot make this small, panel-selected group representative of the population experiencing custody. As a sensitivity check, applying HILDA cross-sectional responding-person weights modestly lowers observed levels but leaves the trajectory shape qualitatively unchanged.

B. First Observed Respondent Prison or Jail Contact. The exposure is the HILDA self-completion questionnaire life-event item, first administered from wave B onwards, asking whether the respondent had been in prison or jail in the previous 12 months. We retain “prison or jail” because it is the HILDA wording. For international readers, the item should be read as respondent self-reported contact with custody in the prior year; the survey does not separate prison from jail as institution types.

Table 1. Sample and prison or jail contact support

Item	Person-waves	Persons
Analytic spine	500,490	50,403
Prison-or-jail item observed (B-X)	318,754	--
Prison-or-jail item missing (B-X)	161,822	--
Ever respondent contact	--	630
Ever family contact	--	2,630
Ever respondent or family	--	2,958
Pre-contact SCQ support	--	474
Post-contact SCQ support	--	501
Person-waves with timing flag	691	--

Notes: Counts are unweighted. SCQ = self-completion questionnaire. Across all wave B–X records in the full analytic spine, the respondent prison-or-jail item is missing in 33.7%. Pre- and post-contact SCQ support count people with at least one valid SCQ observation before or after first observed contact. The timing flag records whether at least one of the four supplementary HILDA indicators for 0–3, 4–6, 7–9, or 10–12 months ago was marked; it is reported for 83.0% of respondent prison-or-jail person-waves.

rather than effects of incarceration.

Table 1 reports support for the exposure measure. Among 50,403 people in the analytic spine, 630 ever report respondent prison or jail contact. A further 2,630 ever report family prison or jail contact, and 2,958 ever report either respondent or family contact. Across all wave B–X records in the full analytic spine, the respondent prison-or-jail item is missing in 33.7%. When the denominator is restricted to adult person-waves with observed age, annual item missingness ranges from 7.6% to 14.3%. The difference reflects the denominator as well as SCQ non-response: the item sits in the questionnaire that respondents complete and return separately after the interview. Among the 630

We define ever observed respondent contact as at least one wave in which this item is reported affirmatively. We define the first observed respondent contact wave as the earliest wave in which the respondent reports such contact. This exposure definition is deliberately literal. First observed respondent contact in HILDA is not necessarily first lifetime incarceration. HILDA does not include a retrospective item recording whether a respondent has ever been incarcerated, so first lifetime custody cannot be identified. Respondents may have had custody experience before entering HILDA, before the item was first asked, between annual waves, or in waves where the SCQ was not completed. The measure also does not distinguish remand, sentenced custody, episode duration, repeated episodes, adult versus youth justice contact, or timing within the past year. For these reasons, the analysis describes trajectories around first observed panel contact

people who ever report respondent contact, 474 have at least one valid pre-contact SCQ observation and 501 have at least one valid post-contact SCQ observation. At first observed contact, the group has a mean age of 35.9 years and is 70% male, and 403 people have both pre- and post-contact SCQ support.

C. Outcome Measures. We examine eleven outcomes observed repeatedly in HILDA. The Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K10) measures non-specific psychological distress over the past four weeks [18, 19]. Higher K10 scores indicate more distress. The SF-36 health survey provides subscales for mental health, physical functioning, general health, and bodily pain, with higher values indicating better health [20]. We also use self-rated health, a single global item rated from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor), coded so that higher values indicate poorer health. Because self-rated health is broad and may reflect both mental and physical health, it is reported as a separate outcome rather than included in the cumulative strain index.

The social and behavioural outcomes are current cigarette smoking, employment, emergency-funds difficulty, and loneliness. Current smoking is a binary measure of whether the respondent currently smokes cigarettes. We interpret smoking as a health-risk and behavioural strain marker, not as psychological strain. Employment is a binary measure of being employed at the time of the annual interview. Emergency-funds difficulty is a binary indicator identifying respondents who report that it would be difficult or impossible to raise funds in an emergency. Loneliness is measured using the HILDA social support item indicating that the respondent often feels very lonely, rated from 1 to 7, with higher values indicating greater loneliness.

BMI is calculated from self-reported height and weight. It is not a component of cumulative strain. Instead, it serves as a boundary or contrast outcome: a slower-moving physical-risk measure included to check whether the main pattern is specific to mental-health, economic, behavioural, and social domains rather than a generic artefact in which every measured outcome worsens around first observed contact.

D. Cumulative Observed Strain. By strain, we mean observed respondent-level health and social adversity in a given wave. The cumulative observed strain index is a transparent descriptive summary of six repeated domains: high K10 psychological distress, low SF-36 mental health, not employed, current smoking, emergency-funds difficulty, and high loneliness. These six were selected because they span the domains consistently emphasised in profiles of Australian prison entrants, namely mental ill-health, unemployment, smoking, financial insecurity, and social isolation [1], and because each is measured repeatedly across waves with a transparent adverse threshold.

The SF-36 physical subscales, self-rated health, and BMI were not included in the index. They capture broader or slower-moving physical-health status and serve as contrast outcomes (Section D). Family prison or jail contact was also not included. It is an important exposure and contextual marker, and we report it in Table 1, but it is not a within-person respondent health or social strain component. Including it would mix respondent outcomes with family custody exposure and would change the index from a respondent-level strain summary into a combined exposure-outcome measure.

Each component was coded as adverse when observed. High K10 distress was defined as $K10 \geq 22$. Low SF-36 mental health was defined as being at or below the 25th percentile in the analytic spine, which was 64.0 in this release. High loneliness was defined as values above the neutral midpoint on the 1–7 agreement scale for the item “I often feel very lonely”. Not employed, current smoking, and emergency-funds difficulty used their binary coding, with a positive endorsement of smoking or emergency-funds difficulty counted as adverse. Current smoking is included as a health-risk and behavioural strain marker rather than as a psychological strain measure.

For each person-wave, we calculated the share of observed components that were adverse, with each observed component weighted equally. The index is cumulative across domains within a person-wave, not over time. The share ranges from 0 to 1 and is reported in percent; the corresponding count of adverse components ranges from 0 to 6 when all six are observed. The denominator is the number of non-missing strain components in that person-wave, not a fixed six-component count for all observations. The index is not a clinical scale, a latent construct, a prediction model, or a causal measure.

3. Analytic Approach

The analysis uses descriptive event-time means among people who ever report respondent prison or jail contact. Event time is defined relative to the first observed respondent contact wave. Negative values indicate years before that first observed wave, zero indicates the first observed contact wave, and positive values indicate years after. Because the HILDA item refers to contact in the past 12 months and the exact custody date is not observed, we interpret the -1 to 0 event-time bin as the contact window rather than as a precisely timed custody onset. Throughout the paper, the contact window refers to this bin: the wave at which contact is first reported and the year preceding it.

An event-time bin is a grouped set of annual observations relative to first observed contact, used to stabilise support and display trajectories. It is not a claim that custody occurred throughout the interval. We group event time, measured in years, into eight bins: ≤ -6 , -5 to -4, -3 to -2, -1 to 0, 1 to 2, 3 to 4, 5 to 6, and ≥ 7 . For each outcome and bin, we report unweighted means among respondents with ever-observed contact and non-missing outcome data. Binary variables are reported as percentages. For SF-36 domains and employment, decreases represent greater strain; for K10, self-rated health, smoking, emergency-funds difficulty, and loneliness, increases represent greater strain. BMI is reported in raw BMI units and is not given a strain direction.

The design is within-group and descriptive. We do not estimate a comparison-group counterfactual, a difference-in-differences model, a fixed-effects treatment effect, or an event-study treatment effect. This is a deliberate design choice. The current HILDA exposure structure and observed pre-contact dynamics make a simple causal interpretation untenable. The paper therefore describes dynamic selection into first observed contact and uses the trajectory structure itself as the object of population-health interest.

4. Results

A. Sample and Exposure Support. Table 1 shows the analytic spine and exposure support. The spine includes 500,490 person-waves from 50,403 people across 24 HILDA waves. Among these respondents, 630 people (1.2%) ever report respondent prison or jail contact in at least one observed wave. A larger group reports family prison or jail contact (2,630 people), and 2,958 people report respondent or family contact. The respondent contact group is therefore small, as expected in a general-population household panel. It is also incompletely observed because the prison-or-jail item sits in the separately returned SCQ; the full-spine and adult annual missingness measures are reported above.

Among the 630 respondents with ever-observed contact, 474 have at least one valid pre-contact SCQ observation, 501 have at least one valid post-contact SCQ observation, and 403 have both. At first observed contact, the group has a mean age of 35.9 years and is 70% male. Across all 630 respondents, valid SCQ observations average 4.7 before contact (median 3, IQR 1-7) and 5.6 after contact (median 4, IQR 1-9). Support varies across event-time bins and outcomes. The contact-window estimates draw on the largest number of observed respondents, while the long pre- and post-contact tails are thinner. Table A1 reports the number of distinct respondents with ever-observed contact contributing to each outcome in each event-time bin.

B. Cumulative Observed Strain. The headline result is the accumulation of observed adverse conditions before first observed respondent prison or jail contact. Figure 1 shows the mean share of adverse observed components

Figure 1. Cumulative observed strain around first observed respondent prison or jail contact. The figure reports the mean share of observed strain components that are adverse among people who ever report respondent prison or jail contact. Components are high K10 distress, low SF-36 mental health, not employed, current smoking, emergency-funds difficulty, and high loneliness. Event time is relative to first observed respondent contact in HILDA, not first lifetime incarceration. Vertical bars show 95% confidence intervals using standard errors clustered by person; the shaded band marks the contact window. The index is descriptive; the y-axis is focused on the observed range and thresholds are unchanged. Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2024; pooled waves.

across six respondent-level domains: high K10 distress, low SF-36 mental health, not employed, current smoking, emergency-funds difficulty, and high loneliness.

Cumulative observed strain rises steadily into the contact window. At least six years before first observed contact, respondents with ever-observed contact have an average of 41% of observed components in the adverse range. This rises to 47% in the -5 to -4 bin, 48% in the -3 to -2 bin, and 53% in the -1 to 0 contact window. Expressed as counts, the mean number of adverse observed components rises from 1.86 in the long pre-contact bin to 2.62 in the contact window. The contact-window value is therefore about 12 percentage points higher than the long pre-contact baseline.

Observed strain is lower in later post-contact bins, reaching 44% in the ≥ 7 bin. Those later bins pool heterogeneous respondents observed at different durations since contact, with possible repeated episodes, selective non-response, and panel attrition. The key descriptive point is the pre-contact accumulation: first observed contact occurs near the visible peak of a multi-domain strain process that is already underway.

Figure 2. Focused strain-oriented heatmap for the main cumulative-strain domains. Values are standardised relative to the long pre-contact bin (≤ -6), with positive values indicating more strain. The heatmap disaggregates the cumulative observed strain index by domain and event-time bin. The bracketed column marks the contact window. The figure is descriptive and does not imply causal effects. Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2024; pooled waves. (0.40 SD), employment (0.37 SD), and SF-36 mental health (0.34 SD). Physical-functioning and general-health changes are smaller, and BMI moves slightly in the opposite direction.

The raw changes in Table 2 show the same structure. Between the long pre-contact bin (≤ -6) and the contact window (-1 to 0), mean K10 psychological distress rises from 19.4 to 22.9, SF-36 mental health falls from 67.3 to 60.5, employment falls from 58.9% to 40.8%, current smoking rises from 53.9% to 60.5%, emergency-funds difficulty rises from 46.8% to 54.6%, and loneliness rises from 3.2 to 3.5. These are the domains that most clearly define the contact-window strain pattern. The levels also indicate a group moving from high strain to higher strain rather than from average to high strain: even six years before contact, mean SF-36 mental health (67.3) sits only modestly above the 25th percentile of the full analytic spine (64.0), and by the contact window it falls below it. Over the same interval, mean K10 crosses the threshold used here for high distress (22).

Figure 2 shows the timing and domain pattern across the six cumulative-strain domains. The cumulative pattern reflects domain-specific changes, with sharper short-run movement in some domains, rather than a uniform shift across all components.

C. Domain-Specific Changes. Figure 3 summarises the change from the long pre-contact bin to the contact window across all domains, with BMI retained as a boundary outcome. Outcomes are oriented so that higher values indicate more strain and are standardised relative to the long pre-contact bin. The largest changes into the contact window are in K10 psychological distress

Figure 3. Change into the first observed respondent-contact window by domain. Outcomes are oriented so that higher values indicate more strain and are standardised relative to the long pre-contact bin (≤ -6). Values show the change from the long pre-contact bin to the contact window. BMI is included as a boundary outcome and is not part of the cumulative observed strain index. Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2024; pooled waves.

The short pre-contact window is also important. Between the -3 to -2 bin and the -1 to 0 contact window, K10 rises by a further 2.2 points, SF-36 mental health falls by a further 3.9 points, employment falls by a further 6.1 percentage points, smoking rises by a further 7.0 percentage points, and emergency-funds difficulty rises by a further 3.2 percentage points. The contact window is therefore not simply a comparison between an adverse exposed group and a stable prior baseline. For several outcomes, the baseline itself is moving.

Table 2. Pre-contact change into the first observed respondent-contact window

Measure	≤ -6	-1 to 0	Δ	-3 to -2	Δ	≥ 7	Δ
K10 psychological distress	19.4	22.9	3.5	20.6	2.2	20.6	-2.2
SF-36 mental health	67.3	60.5	6.8	64.4	3.9	64.9	-4.4
SF-36 physical functioning	79.8	75.0	4.8	76.3	1.3	76.1	-1.1
SF-36 general health	63.3	59.2	4.2	60.8	1.6	59.1	0.1
SF-36 bodily pain	69.2	65.0	4.2	65.1	0.2	62.8	2.2
Self-rated health	2.8	2.9	0.1	2.8	0.1	2.9	0.0
Current smoker	53.9	60.5	6.6	53.5	7.0	50.6	-9.9
Employed	58.9	40.8	18.1	46.8	6.1	54.6	-13.8
Emergency funds difficult	46.8	54.6	7.8	51.4	3.2	46.9	-7.7
Loneliness score	3.2	3.5	0.3	3.4	0.1	3.4	-0.1
BMI	27.4	26.9	-0.5	27.0	-0.0	27.6	0.6

Notes: Means are unweighted event-bin means among people who ever report respondent prison or jail contact. All bins are defined relative to first observed contact. The first Δ is the change from the long pre-contact bin (≤ -6) to the contact window (-1 to 0); the second is the change from the -3 to -2 bin to the contact window; the third is the change from the contact window to the ≥ 7 bin. For percentage indicators, changes are percentage points. For K10, self-rated health, smoking, emergency-funds difficulty and loneliness, positive changes indicate more strain. For SF-36 domains and employment, signs are reversed so positive changes indicate more strain. Scale ranges: K10 10–50; SF-36 domains 0–100; self-rated health 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor); loneliness 1–7; smoking, employment and emergency funds are percentages. BMI is reported in raw units (kg/m^2) and is not part of the cumulative observed strain index.

BMI does not show a consistent contact-window strain pattern.

D. BMI and Physical-Health Boundary Cases. BMI serves as a contrast outcome, and it behaves like one: it does not follow the main strain pattern. Mean BMI is 27.4 in the long pre-contact bin, 26.9 in the contact window, and 27.6 in the long post-contact bin, remaining within the conventional overweight range (25–29.9) throughout. These changes are small and should not be given a favourable health interpretation. Because small BMI movements are directionally ambiguous and too slow-moving to index acute strain, BMI is not treated as a strain component. Its value is interpretive: BMI shows that the results are not a generic artefact in which every measured outcome worsens around first observed contact.

The physical-health domains provide a second boundary. SF-36 physical functioning, general health, bodily pain, and self-rated health are poorer around and after the contact window, but the changes into the window are smaller and the deterioration more gradual and persistent than for the mental health, employment, smoking, financial-strain, and loneliness trajectories. This points to physical-health disadvantage in the observed contact group as more chronic: already present well before contact and less tied to the acute pre-contact escalation captured by the cumulative strain figure.

Taken together, the results support a domain-specific interpretation. First observed respondent prison or jail contact in HILDA appears near the visible peak of an unfolding multi-domain strain process, but the process is not uniform across all outcomes. The strongest evidence concerns psychological distress, mental health, employment, smoking, financial strain, and loneliness. BMI and the physical-health domains show where the pattern stops: the short-run escalation is specific to the mental-health, economic, behavioural, and social domains.

5. Discussion

A. Main Population-Health Interpretation. This paper shows that first observed respondent prison or jail contact in HILDA occurs near the visible peak of an unfolding health and social strain process. The strongest pre-contact deterioration is not confined to one outcome. It appears across K10 psychological distress, SF-36 mental health, employment, current smoking, emergency-funds difficulty, and loneliness. Across these six domains, cumulative observed strain rises from 41% of observed adverse components at least six years before first observed contact to 53% in the contact

window. This is the central population-health result. The movements are not marginal: mean K10 crosses the high-distress threshold (22) between the long pre-contact bin and the contact window, employment falls by nearly a third of its long pre-contact level, and SF-36 mental health falls from just above to below the 25th percentile of the full analytic spine.

The finding matters because the pre-contact period is often treated as a nuisance for causal estimation. In this application, that treatment is backwards: the pre-contact trajectory is the main empirical signal. The years before first observed prison or jail contact are years in which mental health, employment, financial resources, health behaviour, and social connection are already changing in adverse directions. For population health, this period deserves attention in its own right because it is the period in which potentially modifiable needs are already visible, even if HILDA cannot show whether services were available, used, or effective.

The results align with prior work showing that incarceration is embedded in longer histories of disadvantage rather than being the sole origin of health inequality [3, 6, 7, 21]. They also sit alongside recent Australian life-events-calendar evidence among incarcerated mothers, which describes health problems and adversities across the five years before current incarceration; that study sampled women already in prison and used retrospective life-history reports, so it is best read as convergent rather than directly comparable evidence [22]. The current paper extends the Australian evidence base by describing respondent-contact trajectories in HILDA rather than family-member incarceration exposures, which have been the focus of much of the previous HILDA literature [9, 15-17]. The contribution is descriptive but important: it documents the timing and domain-specificity of health and social strain before contact becomes visible in a long-running Australian population panel.

The domain-specificity is central. The strongest movements are in psychological distress, mental health, employment, smoking, emergency-funds difficulty, and loneliness. Physical-health domains deteriorate more gradually and persistently. BMI remains broadly flat. This pattern argues against a simple artefact in which all outcomes mechanically worsen around the contact window because of changes in who is observed at each event time or in how outcomes are measured. It also argues against treating prison or jail contact as a single uniform “shock” with the same association across every health outcome.

B. Service-System Visibility. The results raise a service-system visibility question, but they do not answer it. The domains that deteriorate before first observed contact are domains where health and social systems may have contact points: psychological distress, mental health, employment, smoking, financial strain, and social isolation. HILDA cannot show whether respondents used services, whether services were available, whether support was offered, or whether any support changed the trajectory. The data therefore do not support a judgement about service performance. They do, however, support a narrower and important claim: the deterioration was measurable. It was multi-domain, sustained over several years, and visible in a general-population panel with no access to administrative records. This is detectability in routine panel measures, not evidence that individuals could be accurately classified or targeted from those measures alone.

What HILDA does show is that multi-domain strain is detectable in a general-population panel before first observed respondent prison or jail contact. That observation is important for population-health research because it shifts attention to the years before contact. The relevant questions are how health and social strain intersect with service contact before custody becomes visible, and how those contact points could be used to support people earlier. Australian linkage evidence suggests the justice and health systems interleave well before imprisonment: in a whole-of-population Western Australian study, a third of people with psychiatric illness were arrested over a ten-year period, often before their first recorded contact with mental health services [23]. Linked health, welfare, employment, housing, and justice data could clarify that intersection more directly than HILDA can.

This framing also avoids treating incarceration as the first institutional response to disadvantage. The panel cannot observe the full institutional history. Some respondents may have had earlier justice contact, health-service contact, income support, housing instability, or community-service contact that is not captured here. The contribution is narrower: in the observed HILDA exposure setting, prison or jail contact appears near the visible peak of a multi-domain strain trajectory.

C. Methodological Implications. The HILDA respondent-contact measure is poorly matched to a conventional “effect of incarceration” design. The exposure is a past-year self-reported item from the SCQ, not an administrative custody start date, and first observed contact is not first lifetime incarceration. More substantively, several outcomes are already moving adversely years before the contact window. The exposure therefore appears well after much of the relevant trajectory is underway, and the period that fixed effects and before-after contrasts treat as a baseline is itself part of the deterioration.

This changes how prior HILDA evidence should be read. Within-person models remove stable between-person differences but not time-varying pre-contact deterioration. Prior HILDA fixed-effects work on incarceration-related exposures [9] can also be read as a selection diagnostic: attenuation after adding person fixed effects shows that stable differences explain much of the cross-sectional association, but the remaining within-person estimate may still mix the exposure period with the pre-contact strain arc. The same logic applies to event-study designs. They are more transparent because they make pre-contact dynamics visible, but visibility is not identification. When the pre-contact trajectory is the main empirical feature, it is the result, not a placebo check.

Post-contact movement should be read in the same frame. Lower adverse levels after the contact-window peak do not identify a counterfactual for the contact effect; the bins pool different distances from contact, unknown custody duration, repeated episodes, selective non-response, attrition, and regression to the mean. The substantive contribution of this paper is therefore not a causal estimate but a description of the trajectory that makes simple causal estimates from this exposure structure unreliable. Credible causal work on incarceration and health in this setting requires sharper timing, separation of first lifetime contact from repeated episodes, and a comparison group plausibly following a similar pre-contact trajectory [10, 11]. Linked administrative health, welfare, housing, employment, and justice data are better suited than the HILDA item alone because they can observe custody dates, repeated episodes, service contact, and population groups that household panels under-cover.

A final implication concerns heterogeneity. The trajectories reported here are averages, and averages conceal variation: some respondents will follow steeper or different paths into custody than others. Describing that heterogeneity is the natural next step for prevention-oriented research, but the HILDA contact group is too small to support that profiling. Full-population linked data could both identify heterogeneous trajectories and observe whether services reached the people on them.

6. Limitations

Several limitations follow from the way prison or jail contact is observed in HILDA. The exposure captures the first wave in which a respondent reports prison or jail contact in the panel, which is not necessarily first lifetime incarceration. Respondents may have experienced custody before wave B, between annual waves, in waves where the SCQ was not completed, or before joining the panel. For some respondents, the apparent pre-contact period may therefore include time after an earlier unobserved episode.

The HILDA item does not distinguish adult imprisonment from youth justice contact, and the 12-month lookback can blur episodes occurring near the transition to adulthood. The main analysis follows HILDA’s responding-adult/person structure and does not separately restrict the exposure to adult custody episodes. The descriptive results should therefore be read as respondent prison-or-jail contact as observed by HILDA, not as a clean adult-imprisonment measure.

Excluding first reports before age 18, and a conservative restriction excluding reports before age 19 to account for the past-12-month lookback, leaves the headline cumulative-strain change similar (0.115 and 0.113, respectively, compared with 0.119 in the full sample; Table A2).

The prison or jail contact item is observed in the SCQ and is missing in a substantial share of eligible person-waves. Non-response is unlikely to be random. Periods of custody, housing instability, acute distress, or other forms of disadvantage may reduce questionnaire completion. This can lead to missed contact reports and to selected outcome observation near the contact window.

The observed respondent-contact group is also small and selected. Only 630 respondents ever report respondent

prison or jail contact, and this group is not equivalent to all Australians who experience incarceration. People who are continuously incarcerated, homeless, highly mobile, institutionalised, or otherwise outside the HILDA household panel are less likely to be observed. The HILDA contact group is likely to over-represent people with shorter, intermittent, or otherwise panel-observable contact histories. Support also varies across event-time bins: not every respondent is observed in every bin, so the composition of people contributing to each bin differs. Table [A1](#) documents this variation in bin-level support across measures.

The analysis reports unweighted event-time means among respondents with ever-observed contact. It does not use a comparison group and does not estimate causal effects. The design is appropriate for describing the observed trajectory structure, but it cannot show what would have happened in the absence of prison or jail contact.

The HILDA item also does not distinguish remand, sentenced custody, short episodes, longer episodes, repeated episodes, or timing of incarceration within the past year. These differences may matter for health, but they are averaged together in the descriptive trajectories.

Most health, behaviour, financial-strain, and loneliness measures come from self-report. The cumulative observed strain index uses transparent but imperfect thresholds, including a within-sample percentile threshold for low SF-36 mental health. The index is useful for summarising multi-domain observed strain, but it is not a validated clinical scale, a latent measure, or a prediction model.

Finally, post-contact bins are especially difficult to interpret. Although all bins are defined relative to the same first observed report, they pool people observed at different durations since that report, with possible release and re-entry periods, repeated contact, selective non-response, attrition, and regression to the mean. For this reason, post-contact movement is described as movement away from the contact-window peak, not as an effect of incarceration.

7. Conclusion

First observed respondent prison or jail contact in HILDA appears near the visible peak of an unfolding, multi-domain health and social strain process rather than at its onset. The pattern is domain-specific: psychological distress, SF-36 mental health, employment, smoking, emergency-funds difficulty, and loneliness show the clearest pre-contact deterioration, while physical-health domains change more gradually and BMI is a boundary outcome rather than part of the cumulative observed strain index.

For population health, the years before observed prison or jail contact deserve attention alongside custody and re-entry. For methods, the HILDA respondent-contact measure is poorly matched to a conventional effect-of-incarceration design because fixed effects and before-after contrasts treat as a baseline what is already part of the deterioration. Pre-contact dynamics are the signal, not a nuisance to be controlled away; taking them seriously requires linked administrative data with sharper timing and fuller population coverage.

Data acknowledgement and code availability

This paper uses unit record data from the Household, Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia Survey (HILDA), conducted by the Australian Government Department of Social Services (DSS). The findings and views reported in this paper are those of the authors and should not be attributed to the Australian Government, DSS, or any of DSS' contractors or partners. The analysis uses HILDA Release 24, DOI: [10.26193/6M1BMR](https://doi.org/10.26193/6M1BMR).

HILDA unit-record data are restricted-access and are not redistributed with this paper. Researchers wishing to reproduce the analysis should obtain HILDA access through the official data access arrangements. The replication package, including the Stata code, documentation, file manifest, successful-run log, aggregate output tables, and generated figures, is available on Zenodo: [10.5281/zenodo.20949942](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20949942). The analysis is reproducible for authorised HILDA users once the required HILDA files are installed locally.

Appendix

Event-time support by measure. Table A1 reports the number of distinct respondents with ever-observed contact contributing to each outcome in each event-time bin. Event time is relative to first observed respondent prison or jail contact in HILDA, not first lifetime incarceration.

Table A1. Persons contributing to each event-time bin

Measure	≤ -6	-5 to -4	-3 to -2	-1 to 0	1 to 2	3 to 4	5 to 6	≥ 7
Cumulative observed strain	283	342	418	630	514	402	344	279
K10 psychological distress	171	175	233	400	323	287	246	237
SF-36 mental health	264	306	367	628	459	364	311	267
SF-36 physical functioning	263	306	363	619	460	362	311	269
SF-36 general health	264	297	363	625	458	364	310	268
SF-36 bodily pain	264	309	365	628	461	364	311	269
Self-rated health	265	308	365	628	460	363	311	269
Current smoker	244	287	346	625	457	363	309	267
Employment	283	342	418	630	514	402	344	279
Emergency-funds difficulty	262	300	359	609	447	353	307	263
Loneliness	261	303	365	625	454	359	306	269
BMI	180	214	270	484	388	345	295	262

Notes: Counts are distinct people who ever report respondent prison or jail contact and have a non-missing observation for the relevant measure in the relevant event-time bin.

Sensitivity checks. One concern is that first observed reports at younger ages may partly capture youth justice contact rather than adult imprisonment. Youth justice custody is a different institutional setting, and HILDA's past-12-month wording means that a report at age 18 could still refer to contact before age 18. This affects a small minority of the observed respondent-contact group: 48 of 630 people (7.6%) were first observed before age 18, and 61 of 630 (9.7%) were first observed before age 19. Table A2 therefore repeats the main sensitivity quantities after excluding first observed reports before age 18 and, more conservatively, before age 19. The cumulative strain change remains similar across the original, age ≥ 18, and age ≥ 19 samples: 0.119, 0.115, and 0.113, respectively.

Table A2. Sensitivity to age at first observed respondent prison or jail report

Measure	Original	Age ≥ 18	Age ≥ 19
Ever-contact people	630	582	569
Any pre-contact SCQ support	474	458	449
Any post-contact SCQ support	501	466	455
Both pre- and post-contact SCQ support	403	388	380
Cumulative strain, ≤ -6	0.414	0.414	0.414
Cumulative strain, -1 to 0	0.534	0.529	0.527
Cumulative strain change	0.119	0.115	0.113
K10 psychological distress change	3.48	3.38	3.45
SF-36 mental health change	6.78	7.05	7.02
SF-36 physical functioning change	4.85	5.05	5.28
SF-36 general health change	4.16	4.64	4.72
SF-36 bodily pain change	4.23	4.74	5.08
Self-rated health change	0.10	0.13	0.14
Current smoking change	6.57	6.94	6.62
Employment change	18.08	16.31	15.87
Emergency-funds difficulty change	7.79	6.45	5.95
Loneliness change	0.31	0.32	0.32
BMI change	-0.46	-0.29	-0.25

Notes: Age is measured at the first wave in which respondent prison or jail contact is observed. The age ≥ 19 restriction is conservative for the item's past-12-month lookback. Domain changes are oriented so positive values indicate greater strain, except BMI. Smoking, employment, and emergency-funds changes are percentage points; other changes are scale points.

Individual outcome trajectories. Figures A1–A11 show the individual outcome trajectories underlying the aggregate patterns reported in the main text. Each plot shows unweighted means or percentages among people who ever report respondent prison or jail contact. Higher values indicate greater strain for K10 psychological distress, self-rated health, current smoking, emergency-funds difficulty, and loneliness. Lower values indicate greater strain for the SF-36 outcomes and employment. BMI is retained as a boundary outcome and is not assigned a strain direction. Scale ranges are: K10 10–50; SF-36 domains 0–100; self-rated health 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor); loneliness 1–7; BMI in kg/m²; smoking, employment, and emergency-funds difficulty are percentages.

Figure A1. K10 psychological distress trajectory.

Figure A2. SF-36 mental health trajectory.

Figure A3. SF-36 physical functioning trajectory.

Figure A4. SF-36 general health trajectory.

Figure A5. SF-36 bodily pain trajectory.

Figure A6. Self-rated health trajectory.

Figure A7. Current smoking trajectory.

Figure A8. Employment trajectory.

Figure A9. Emergency-funds difficulty trajectory.

Figure A10. Loneliness trajectory.

Figure A11. BMI trajectory.

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